

Research report on the institutional implementation of the Erasmus+ traineeships at Higher Educational Institutions' level

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About DETAS

DETAS (Digitalising Erasmus Traineeship Application Support) is an innovative project designed to enhance the Erasmus+ traineeship experience for students, universities, and host organisations. It seeks to address the growing demand for high-quality traineeships across Europe by upgrading and digitalising the Erasmus+ Intern portal. The project aligns with key EU policies such as the European Strategy for Universities, the Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027), and the European Year of Skills, with a focus on digital transformation and employability.

By improving the Erasmus+ Intern portal, DETAS aims to increase the number of Erasmus+ traineeships, which currently supports around 75,000 participants, with the goal of reaching 100,000 annually. The project focuses on providing students with better access to resources, supporting their journey from pre-departure to on-site traineeships, and streamlining the recruitment process for companies. DETAS will implement a series of capacity-building activities, policy recommendations, and technical innovations to ensure that the portal remains a vital tool for connecting students and companies across Europe.

DETAS will also address challenges faced by Erasmus+ trainees, such as local integration, pre-departure support, and on-site assistance, ensuring that the experience benefits both students and host organisations. Through collaboration with key partners, the project will create a more efficient and accessible platform that supports youth employability and digital skills development across Europe.

The DETAS project spans three years, from January 2024 to December 2026, structured into distinct phases to ensure a comprehensive approach to improving Erasmus+ traineeships. The first year focuses on needs analysis, research, and the development of a technical blueprint, which includes this desk research and survey to assess key areas for innovation. In 2025, the project will transition into implementing innovations on ErasmusIntern.org, alongside developing traineeship quality labels and improved guidelines for universities. The final year will see the technical release of the enhanced platform, advocacy efforts, and policy recommendations based on the project's findings.

1. General Introduction

1. General Introduction

With over 14 million total participants since its inception in 1987, the Erasmus+ programme is one of the most recognisable programmes of the European Union. For many in the general public, the student aspect of the programme has become synonymous with study mobility. However, the Erasmus+ programme has since 2014 supported Erasmus+ traineeship which now accounts for 90,000 yearly student participants¹. Understanding that the growth of this type of mobility has impacted European, national and local stakeholders, this report looks at the current support structures in place at European Higher Educational institutions (hereafter HEI) to support Erasmus+ traineeships.

Hence, this report assesses the current state of play of traineeship in HEIs and seeks to answer what educational professionals, namely those in contact with supporting sending students on Erasmus+, have created for strategies to get students acquainted and interested in participating in the traineeships programme. The report starts with a literature review which examines what Erasmus+ traineeships are and what has been developed at HEIs to support students and employers in participating in the programme and hosting students at their companies. Thereafter, the report explores the methodology of the study that was carried out for the report. It consists of a survey sent out in early 2025 until April to European HEIs with over 100 answers in addition to 6 focus groups sessions with international relations officers (hereafter IROs) covering the support provided to students before, during and after the traineeship abroad.

Thereafter, the report dives into the findings of the survey and finds two thirds of HEIs have supporting activities for students that wish to go on Erasmus+ traineeship. This section also looks at the kinds of support that HEIs tend to provide to students and whether HEIs do outreach to companies. The following section examines the findings of the IRO focus groups which confirms that HEIs mainly support Erasmus+ traineeships before the student departs. However, helping these students during and after the traineeship are stages of support that some HEIs have been developing in recent years. Overall, this report seeks to establish the current status of support for European traineeships at HEIs before, during and after a student traineeship.

¹ European Court of Auditors, (2024). *EU actions addressing traineeships for young people*
https://www.eca.europa.eu/ECAPublications/RV-2024-01/RV-2024-01_EN.pdf

2. Brief Literature Review

2. Brief Literature Review

Backdrop²

Recent decades have seen a significant growth in international education initiatives within the higher education sector. This is based on the expansion in the numbers of students undertaking global traineeships as part of their higher education studies (Di Pietro, 2022; Twomey and Cvitan, 2017). There is evidence that global work experience prepares future graduates for an interconnected world, and equips them with the skills necessary to thrive into a globalised workforce (De Wit, 2020). It is further argued that such experience confers a distinct employability advantage on students. As such, it conveys to employers a sense of confidence, self-reliance, social aptitude, and intercultural competence, as well as representing a formal record of working in a global professional context (Cranston et al, 2020; Kattiyapornpong & Almeida, 2022). Although the literature underscores a marked increase in interest and participation in global traineeships for higher education students, it is notable that it also points to a dearth of research in the area (Lazarova et al, 2022).

International Student Trainee...a specific category of organisational newcomer

Undertaking a traineeship can be an exciting and sometimes fraught experience for higher education students. The experience tests their existing frameworks of understanding, and it disrupts their zones of comfort. It demands of them to move from their student identity to one of a professional neophyte. It forces them to leave the familiarity and inclusionary comfort of their university lives and associated support systems; and they must adapt to their host organisation's norms, pace, rules, and assessment systems in order to become a fully functioning organisational member (Twomey & Pretti, 2022).

Furthermore, in the case of international traineeships, students are required to move to another country and cultural context. The literature highlights the intensified experiences of change, challenge, adjustment and learnings associated with international internships (Hollis, 2012; Yeom & Bae, 2010). Specific issues cited in the discourse include navigating intercultural differences, language barriers, differences in workplace behaviours, legal requirements, financial resources and costs, and fear of separation from family and friends, (Wijbenga et al, 2023; Penneforte, 2024). Of interest is recent research by

² From more insights on the literature review: Rommane, S., & Twomey, P. (2025) From Digital Gaps to Seamless Journeys: Insights into the Erasmus+ Traineeship Experience. https://detas.erasmusintern.org/publications/desk_research_traineeship_exp.pdf

Pennaforte (2025) on the ways in which the process of organisational socialisation unfolds in the context of extended international internships.

Supporting Students on International Traineeships

As any other international students, traineeships students also need support to adjust in this new environment. Peterson et al. (2017) point to the importance of purposeful, adequate, and effective preparation of students for traineeships. Such preparation supports students in the boundary passage from academia to the workplace, optimising their learning outcomes, and performance (Winchester-Seeto & Rowe, 2023; Jackson et al, 2015).

Widely differing approaches to the preparation of students by higher education institutions emerge across the literature review. Distinctions in preparatory programmes include formal vs. informal; assessed vs. unassessed, credit-bearing vs. non-credit-bearing; compulsory participation vs. optional; pre-departure assignments vs. none; individual vs. group delivery; and durations ranging from weekend- to semester-long (Dunlap & Mapp, 2017). In their model, Winchester-Seeto & Rowe (2023) highlight three intersecting areas of traineeship preparation viz. practical matters, learning, and emotional aspects. The importance of raising students' awareness of employer and higher education institutions' expectations, and their own responsibilities, receives considerable attention (Salter et al, 2021; Fleming et al, 2023). It is suggested that, in advance of their traineeships, students be made aware of the role that proactive behaviours play in students' successful integration during placement (Pennaforte, 2025). Such behaviours have been shown to be positively associated with relationship building, role clarity, and social integration by newcomers into their organisations (Bauer & Erdogan, 2012; Cooper-Thomas et al, 2012).

A number of specific preparation strategies emerge from the literature review. These include the use of case scenarios designed to challenge students with potential issues around international traineeships e.g., work, finance, well-being, and socialisation (Trede & Flowers, 2020); supporting students in defining and reflecting on learning goals (Gates, 2014); simulation tools, including international business simulations (Schech et al, 2017); meetings with returning peers; and preparatory work in a group setting that is designed around sharing and reflection (Billett, 2015). Magnus (2009) found that one-to-one interviews between students and their host organisation supervisor in advance of placement can be particularly effective in reducing student stress and ambiguity. Such pre-traineeship support can build students' resilience so that they can better manage the

challenges and tensions associated with transitioning from the classroom to the workplace (Coll and Chapman 2000).

In the specific context of international traineeships, students need to be prepared for logistical and risk management issues e.g., international travel, local legislative and taxation issue, homesickness, stress management, self-care, and motivation (Ramji, Kines et al. 2021; Salter, Halbert et al. 2021). According to Trede, Bowles et al. (2013), immersion in a new culture alone does not guarantee that students will acquire intercultural competences during their international internship. For this reason, higher education institutions should provision a pedagogical offering that supports students in developing an awareness of their own cultural values and in heightening their awareness of other cultures prior to their internships (Engstrom & Jones, 2007). As such, theories and frameworks of intercultural development and cross-cultural competence should be an integral component of students' traineeship preparation. In this context, frameworks have been designed to support higher education students in the development of their cultural awareness (Deardorff, 2010). By leveraging this targeted approach, higher education institutions may encourage students to engage in critical self-reflection that, in turn, enhances their self-awareness, reduces culture shock, and optimises intercultural learning (McRae, Ramji et al, 2016; Dunlap & Mapp, 2017).

Employer preparation is a critical component of successful global traineeships. Peterson et al. (2017) argue that higher education institutions should ensure that host employers and supervisors are well-informed regarding the scope of the traineeships and knowledge level of the student. This mitigates any potential disconnect between expectations and realities, which can cause stress for both stakeholders. Edwards et al. (2015) recommend clear induction processes at the start of the placement. The role of the employer is acknowledged in the literature, in particular relationships between the student and their supervisor and co-workers, dimensions that have been shown to be correlated to students' task mastery (Toncar & Cudmore, 2000; Twomey, 2019).

Even with cultural preparation, students often feel overwhelmed by differences in work practices on international internships. In this context, Gribble et al. (2014) suggest that supervisors should be made aware of the impact of a new environment on such students, who are essentially professional newcomers grappling with a different cultural context. Thampi (2017) highlights the value of a "buddy system" in the host organisation, as a means of mitigating such feelings of loneliness and culture shock during the traineeship.

Finally, Magnus (2009) recommends that students journal during their traineeship as it is effective in reducing stress.

Conclusions

Higher education institutions can play a crucial role in preparing students and employers for international traineeships, and the literature review highlights a range of ways in which they can support stakeholders. Effective preparation involves a multifaceted approach that includes robust preparatory programmes, intercultural development, and active employer involvement. In leveraging such approaches, higher education institutions can support students and employers in navigating the complexities of the international traineeship experience from both perspectives, and in so doing, optimise successful outcomes for all stakeholders.

However, it should be noted that the scholarly discourse yields very little in terms of offering specific, practical solutions for improvements in student preparation (Matthew & Lough, 2017). The DETAS primary research may address some of these knowledge gaps. Finally, it is acknowledged in the literature that there is a challenge in striking a pragmatic balance between the ideal standards for preparation and supervision, and the downward pressures on resources – both human and financial – as is observable across the higher education sector (Tan et al, 2016).

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3. Methodology

3. Methodology

To analyse what strategies and activities currently exist at European HEIs to support students in participating in Erasmus+ traineeships, two research methods are used, in a mixed approach. Specifically, the DETAS project conducted a survey with European HEIs and organised online focus groups in the first half of 2025. In the survey, quantitative data was collected while qualitative data was extracted from the focus groups. In both cases, the target group were personnel of HEIs who work on sending students on Erasmus+ traineeships.

The choice of this mixed methods approach provides this research with the necessary in-depth understanding of the existing support measures that HEIs of Erasmus+ programme countries offer to their students, as revealed through focus groups. Whereas the survey seeks to map the current adoption of the strategies and activities. Combined, these methods provide insights into the latest on-the-ground realities of HEI promotion Erasmus+ traineeships and indicate where professionals believe improvements are needed to further develop the Erasmus+ traineeship success.

3.1 DETAS Higher educational institutions survey

A survey of HEI staff working on sending and supporting Erasmus+ traineeship was conducted at the beginning of 2025. The online survey was disseminated between January and April 15th 2025. The target group of the survey was HEI staff members who help students to pursue Erasmus+ traineeships opportunities. This choice is based on the staff's responsibility of being the informational access point for Erasmus+ traineeships and for their proximity to the students. A total of 137 responses were collected.

The primary methods of dissemination included sending direct invitations to HEI staff working on sending Erasmus+ traineeships to complete the survey. These channels included the EUF's internal mailing newsletter, which reaches over 90 European HEIs, and the organisation's external emailing list. All the communication was done in English. Furthermore, the project partners published multiple posts on social media inviting higher educational staff supporting international traineeships to participate in the survey and HEI project partners of the West University of Timișoara, University of Limerick, University of Latvia and the University of Pavia disseminated the survey through their European University Alliance networks and national higher education colleagues.

Participation in the survey was voluntary. The survey relied on participants' self-identification as the anonymity of the respondents needed to be secured. The survey followed the regulations of GDPR of the European Union to secure the process of information and integrity of the data. Furthermore, the survey language was English, as it was assumed that international relations officers and other relevant HEI staff who send students on Erasmus+ have an appropriate level of understanding of the language. However, project partners were given the freedom to communicate in their local language to distribute the survey to regional and or national higher education networks. The latter was done in order to get as many HEI staff as possible to answer the survey.

Representativeness

The survey's target group focused on staff members responsible for sending students on Erasmus+ traineeships. With the Erasmus+ programme countries predominantly located on the European continent, the representativeness of the research was ensured by having all regions of Europe represented in the survey responses. This geographical survey representation aims to ensure that no region is either severely overrepresented or underrepresented.

The identified regions of survey responses are the following:

Baltics: Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania.

Nordics: Denmark, Finland, Sweden and Norway.

Western Europe: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Switzerland and the United Kingdom.

Central and Eastern Europe: Albania, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Poland, Slovenia and Slovakia.

Southern European countries: Italy, Spain, Greece, Portugal.

Data presentation in the report

The survey data is presented through percentages rather than raw numbers to highlight proportional differences among the responses. All results are rounded to the nearest whole number for clarity and ease of interpretation. To visually represent the distribution of categorical responses, pie charts are used, providing an intuitive overview of how participants' answers are divided across categories.

3.2 DETAS Higher educational institutions focus groups

To complement the quantitative data collected via the survey, a series of focus groups were organised in March 2025 to gather in-depth qualitative insights from staff members working on sending students on Erasmus+ traineeships. The rationale for conducting focus groups is to explore staff experiences in offering traineeship support and information to students and to explore the needs of the higher education sector for improving the aid offer. Additionally, the focus groups enabled staff members from different regions and institutions to share common perspectives by reflecting on what they take for granted and what they can learn from their peers. This enhances the chances of innovative HEI or European-level ideas to support Erasmus+ traineeships.

To objectively assess the tailored support provided at different stages of the traineeship process, three stages are identified. These are: the pre-stage, the during stage and after stage the traineeship journey. Figure 1 illustrates that the pre-stage support encompasses the support that is provided from the day the student enters the HEI until when the student leaves for the traineeship. The second stage is the support provided by HEI staff during the traineeship; this period is the time between when the student arrives at the location and the last day of the traineeship. Lastly, there is the after stage, which is the support that HEI offers to students after the last day of the internship.

Figure 1: Stages of HEI Traineeship support-

before, during and after

Once the participants joined the focus group, they are divided into six breakout rooms.

- Two focus groups focused on HEI support to students before the traineeship starts
- Two focus groups focused on HEI support to students during the traineeship
- Two focus groups focused on HEI support to students after the traineeship ends

A total of 52 participants, of higher education staff working on Erasmus + traineeships joined the online focus group sessions (around 45 minutes) to share their experiences. Each of the groups also had a moderator from the consortium staff who guided the discussions. A total of three focus groups were guided by project staff of the University of Limerick, two were guided by staff of EUF and one by ESN. These project partners developed questions independently and shared them with their counterparts in the preparation of the focus groups. These questions served to develop a semi-structured questioning method involving the main question and subquestions.

The data from the focus groups was collected through digital recording using the Zoom digital recording measure. All moderators created a summary of what was discussed in their sessions. These summaries of the notes were thereafter coded to look at the patterns of the different themed focus group responses.

Focus group questions

During the focus groups, participants were asked about the types of support their institutions provide to students before, during, and after their Erasmus+ traineeship. Before the traineeship, the sessions explored what guidance and tools are offered to help students find placements, prepare for their experience, and develop necessary skills. During the traineeship, the sessions discussed when problems typically arise, how institutions intervene to support students in resolving issues, and what kinds of assistance might be missing. Finally, the last sessions asked how institutions help students reflect on their international experiences after the traineeship, including whether they provide structured post-mobility debriefing through workshops, mentoring, or reflection sessions.

Limitations to the research

When interpreting the findings of this report, readers should be aware of several limitations. The survey and focus group samples largely reflect the EUF network's and partner organisations membership and social media subscribers, which may limit representativeness. As the data is self-reported, it relies on participants' self-identification and may include subjective bias. Both activities were conducted only in English, possibly excluding non-English-speaking Erasmus+ HEI staff. Additionally, participants were randomly assigned to focus groups, so some staff may not have discussed the stage of mobility they specialize in. Finally, variations in how figures were reported may have affected data consistency.

4. Survey Analysis

4. Survey Analysis

The survey generated 137 responses from 127 Higher education institutions (HEI). They represented a range of institutional types as detailed in Figure 2. Responses were analysed across a number of criteria aligned to the questionnaire construct. The purpose of the findings was to achieve a fuller understanding of how higher education institutions support students in international traineeships, and to provide direction for future enhancements and developments.

Figure 2. Type of institution

Responses and Participation by Country

As presented in Figure 3, responses were received from 39 countries. Based on the countries that responded to the survey, a total of 42,859 students participated in Erasmus+ mobility programmes, including both study periods and traineeships. Institutional participation varied widely, ranging from 2,055 students at the highest to just 1 at the lowest, with an overall average of 309 participants. During the same period, 12,793 students undertook Erasmus+ traineeships. Participation in traineeships also showed significant variation across HEIs, with totals ranging from 877 students to none, resulting in an average of 97 traineeship participants.

Figure 3. Responses by country

HEI supports offered to students in finding international traineeships

Respondents were asked to detail what assistance they provide to students in relation to finding international traineeships. As seen in Figure 4, two-thirds (66.42%) of HEIs reported that they provide support to their students. 5.84% of HEIs offer support that is partial or conditional (dependent on department, subject to specific programmes or individual staff). 14.6% HEIs reported that they offer information support only. And only 11.7% stated that they offer no assistance to their students.

The responses indicate that the levels and nature of institutional support to students vary widely. On a positive note, over 86% of HEIs offer some level of support, which suggests that HEIs assign some value to the importance of such provision for students undertaking international traineeships. However, the data suggest an inconsistency of provision that may mean some students receive robust guidance, whilst others must navigate the process in the absence of appropriate (if any) support.

Figure 4. Assistance offered to students in finding international traineeships

Looking at the data in Figure 5, the most frequently reported category of support is “**guidance on finding placement**”, cited by over 70% of respondents. This shows that European HEIs assign a high priority to helping to locate and identify global traineeship opportunities. Examples of guidance instruments include advice sessions, informational materials, and access to staff with experience in international mobility. The second most cited category of support is “**sharing addresses of online job portals**”, as reported by almost six in ten respondents. This category is concerned with direct access to external resources and jobs boards.

“**Partnerships with companies or organisations**” emerged as a significant form of support and was mentioned by over 50% of respondents. This is because such partnerships can be instrumental in streamlining the placement process, providing access to actual, institutionally-known opportunities that enhance students’ chances of securing internship opportunities.

Less common were “**job fairs or networking events**”, cited by almost one in five respondents. This is interesting to assess as these events can be particularly effective in connecting students with potential employers and fostering professional skills, such as networking, in real-time settings.

“**Other forms of support**”, including alumni networks, internal databases, and informal referrals are offered by a smaller number of institutions. This shows the diversity of approaches and perhaps some potential for innovation.

Figure 5. Types of supports offered by HEIs to help students secure international traineeships

Figure 6 details the specific ways in which HEIs prepare their students for international traineeships. As can be seen from the graph, the results reveal a diverse and multifaceted approach to this endeavour, with 83% of respondents choosing more than one support option. Looking at the graph, the most commonly cited support is “**pre-departure orientations**”, reported by almost 60% of respondents. Such sessions serve as a foundational step in helping students to understand and manage logistical, cultural, and academic expectations before embarking on their placements.

Closely following is “**one-to-one preparatory discussions**” at 43%. This form of support may be particularly valuable in addressing individual student needs, concerns and questions and also help the HEI assess a student’s readiness for an international traineeship. The importance of language is reflected in the use of “**language training**” as a support by more than a third of respondents. Furthermore, “**cultural awareness training**” is also cited by three out of ten respondents which shows that less than half of institutions prepare for cultural shock due to an Erasmus+ traineeship. Understanding that Erasmus+ is meant for students to gain intercultural experience, this may be a weaker point in support currently offered by HEIs.

Additionally, “**CV & Interview Workshops**” were commonly reported (35.8%) as supports, reflecting the importance assigned by HEIs to the application, recruitment and selection processes for traineeships. Understanding the role of workplace readiness in a global context, almost a fifth of respondents offered specific workshops on “**professional skills**”. Less frequently, HEIs offer “**country briefings**” (12.4%) and “**resilience training**” (6.6%), which, while less common, can be critical in preparing students for the emotional and situational challenges of living and working abroad. Of concern is that 11.7% of institutions reported that they offer students no preparatory support at all.

Figure 6. Ways in which higher education institutions prepare students for their international traineeships

Availability of additional financial supports for students

The following graph (Figure 7) shows that just 31.4% of institutions offer additional financial support to students undertaking international traineeships (in addition to the Erasmus+ funding). Research³ suggests that the baseline Erasmus+ grant does not cover all costs associated with their traineeship mobility and the data presented in Figure 7 would appear to support this contention.

³ Alves, H., Spröge, K., & Bacelar, J. (2024). Removing the main obstacles to European student mobility. European University Foundation. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11145764>

Figure 7. Extra financial support for students undertaking international traineeships (in addition to the Erasmus+ funding)

Institutional mechanisms in place to raise awareness of Erasmus+ and international traineeships

In relation to specific HEI supports used to promote Erasmus+ and international traineeships, Figure 8 suggests that institutions use a mix of mechanisms. The data show that nearly 86% of institutions organise “**information sessions**” for students, making this the most common support mechanism. These sessions may serve as a key starting point for raising awareness, answering questions, and encouraging participation in international mobility programmes. Over three-quarters (77%) of respondents reported having a “**dedicated office or staff**” responsible for managing Erasmus+ and traineeship activities. This is suggestive of an institutional commitment to providing structured, accessible support for students navigating international opportunities.

54% of HEIs offer students “**financial support**” in the form of scholarships or grants, possibly lowering the financial barriers to entry to international traineeships for some students. Perhaps not surprisingly, “**partnerships with organisations**” abroad were reported by 38% of institutions. These partnerships are key to securing opportunities for traineeship placements and fostering long-term international collaboration. They are suggestive of a strategic effort on the part of some HEIs to build employer relationships and create a sustainable pipeline of trainee opportunities. Finally, a small but notable 6%

of institutions mentioned “*other mechanisms*”, including promotional campaigns, intranet resources, and collaborations with organisations like AIESEC. These responses highlight the diversity and creativity in the promotion domain.

Figure 8. Institutional support mechanisms in place to promote Erasmus+ and international traineeships

Ways in which HEIs engage with employers to secure traineeship opportunities for students

In relation to how HEIs engage with employers, Figure 9 shows that employer partnerships and networking events are the most common mechanism. Other conduits include networking events, online portals and careers fairs. Certainly the results suggest that there is significant potential for HEIs to leverage employer engagement in order to optimise student chances of securing an international traineeship.

Figure 9. Ways in which HEIs engage with employers to secure traineeship opportunities for students

Facilitating students' adjustment to living and working in a foreign country

Looking at Figure 10, ***“feedback and debriefing sessions”*** are the most common forms of support, as reported by almost half of respondents. ***“Counselling services”*** and ***“local support networks”*** also feature relatively strongly. Of note and concern is that over a quarter of institutions report that they have no support mechanisms in place.

The ***“other”*** category included online tools that provide country-specific information, and student internship reports with tips on the internship and the country/city in question. In addition, self-reflective reports and one-to-one meetings to review progress and issues were mentioned as supports.

Figure 10. How HEIs facilitate their students' adjustment to living and working in a foreign country during their traineeships

Typical challenges faced by students

Figure 11 shows that, by a significant margin, **“financial constraints”** emerged as the greatest challenge. Cited by 74% of respondents, it demonstrates that students regularly struggle with the cost of living abroad and this may pose a barrier to entry to international traineeships for many students. **“Cultural adaptation”** (45%) and **“language barriers”** remains a significant hurdle. In this context, students may face challenges in understanding local customs, social norms, and workplace cultures which may affect their integration. A significant number of respondents noted difficulties associated with **“transitioning to the world of work”** (42%). **“Homesickness”** was mentioned by over a third of respondents (36%). This reveals that being away from familiar environments, family and friends can be very challenging for students and may affect their overall experience.

Participants were asked to list additional challenges of traineeships that are different from the study mobility experience. **Accommodation and living arrangements** emerged as the most frequently cited challenge. Unlike study mobility, trainees often lack access to university housing and must navigate competitive housing markets independently.

Finding and securing placements can be more challenging for students as many HEIs do not routinely offer the facility to find placements for their students. Accordingly, students

are working independently to do so – often against a backdrop of a very competitive landscape.

Workplace isolation and lack of peer support was cited as an issue, particularly where there are no other students on placement in the organisation/local area, thus offering fewer social outlets. **Visa and administrative barriers** were noted as more problematic in the traineeship context. **Mismatch of expectations** between students and host organisations emerges as a common difference between study and traineeships, with trainees often struggling with demanding tasks, making the leap from student to a new professional identity, and adapting to workplace behaviours, norms and expectations.

Figure 11. Typical challenges faced by students participating in international internships

In addition to the data shown in Figure 11, it is interesting to share some of the quotes from respondents:

“Integration into the local community is harder for trainees than students. Students tend to be in a more socially active environment and get offered activities for the purpose of integration, while trainees often don't get such a chance.”

“Support is focused on studies, therefore the trainees can sometimes be left on their own and do a lot of things independently.”

Assessment of the effectiveness of institutional support for students

As Figure 12 demonstrates, the most common method for evaluating support is through “**student surveys or feedback forms**”, used by almost 70% of HEIs. This indicates a strong reliance on direct student input to gauge effectiveness of the traineeship. “**Follow-up interviews**” and “**employer feedback**” are also used but to a much lesser extent. This may be due to a lack of resources that HEIs have, however to correctly understand how the Erasmus+ traineeship went, this qualitative form of engagement should be taken more into account. Some HEIs may want to sample some of their returning student trainees when they come back. “**Academic performance evaluation**” is used by only 30% of institutions, suggesting that the link between traineeship outcomes and academic metrics may be an area for development. This is most likely the case for traineeships that are a part of the mandatory activity in the student curriculum. .

A concerning minority of institutions do not provide feedback to students or indeed evaluate traineeships at all. This may reflect resource constraints or differing institutional priorities. A number of institutions mentioned innovative or informal methods, such as departmental assessments and podcast interviews with returning students.

Figure 12. Ways in which the effectiveness of support for students participating in international placements are assessed by the HEI

Suggestions for improvements around student supports

Respondents were asked for suggestions on changes or improvements that might enhance support for students undertaking international traineeships. Based on the analysis, a number of key themes emerged:

The lack of financial support is clearly an issue, with many respondents citing the need for increased grants or financial aid to cover the rising cost of living and travel. Another recurring theme was **the lack of institutional support**, in particular the need for more dedicated staff and structured support systems. Ensuring **stronger employer engagement** was also cited by respondents as being key to ensuring quality traineeships. **Better communication and guidance** were suggested as improvements, specifically around clarity of information, better pre-departure preparation, and more accessible resources. Other suggestions included more simplified administration, increased accommodation support, better language and cultural preparation, and enhanced structures for monitoring and evaluation of traineeships.

Some of the comments of the respondents are captured below:

"Simplify the Erasmus+ mobility procedure (less administration, no one cares about the Learning Agreement for traineeship)"

"Staff is needed at HEIs, this should also be mentioned in any policy recommendations."

"More Erasmus resources in the university (not enough people to cover all aspects of a placement abroad)."

Observed benefits of international student traineeships

Figure 13 presents the benefits of international traineeships as observed by the respondents. **"Personal growth"** is the most widely recognised benefit, with nearly nine in ten institutions observing enhanced personal development among traineeship participants. High value is attached to **"Language acquisition"** and **"intercultural competence"**, reflecting the immersive nature of international experiences. **"Confidence building"** is another major outcome, stemming from students having to navigate new environments and responsibilities. **"Employability"** is recognised by over two-thirds of

respondents, underscoring the career value of international work experience. This reflects many of the findings of the scholarly discourse, as highlighted in the DETAS desk research on the current state of Erasmus+ traineeships reviews⁴.

Of the 137 respondents, 131 institutions (95.6%) selected more than one benefit. These findings suggest that international traineeships are not only academically enriching but also play a critical role in shaping well-rounded, globally competent graduates.

Figure 13. Benefits of international traineeships for students from the HEI perspective

HEIs' familiarity with and usage of the erasmusintern.org portal

The [Erasmusintern.org](https://erasmusintern.org) website is a tool for students to see available traineeships and for companies to publish traineeships online. For these reasons, the survey also asked HEI staff whether they use the portal to help students secure a traineeship.

The results presented in Figure 14 show that just over half of the institutions are aware of the erasmusIntern.org portal, suggesting a moderate level of visibility across the higher education sector. However, the fact that nearly 44% of institutions are unfamiliar with the platform highlights a potential opportunity for increased promotion. Overall, this suggests

⁴ Rommane, S., & Twoney, P. (2025) From Digital Gaps to Seamless Journeys: Insights into the Erasmus+ Traineeship Experience. https://detas.erasmusintern.org/publications/desk_research_traineeship_exp.pdf

that there is much room for improvement in the erasmusintern.org usage by HEI staff and that more students could be reached by the platform when the HEI staff sending students on Erasmus+ traineeships familiarity figures of the portal increases.

Figure 14. Respondents' familiarity with erasmusintern.org portal

As seen in Figure 15, fewer than half of the institutions that are familiar with the erasmuintern.org portal actually use it to source opportunities for their students. This is suggestive of a gap between awareness of the portal and its application in practice.

Figure 15. Use of erasmusintern.org portal for sourcing traineeship opportunities

Figure 16 focuses on frequency of use of the portal by the HEIs. (Note that only those respondents who have an awareness of the portal were asked this question). The results show that almost half of HEIs use the portal sometimes to help students in securing traineeships, with 14% using it always. 37% of respondents reported that they never use the portal. Separately, respondents were asked to rate the usability of the portal on a scale of 1-7. 42.9% of respondents assigned it a rating of 5 out of 7. 15.6% rated it at 6. 6.5% gave it the highest score of 7. A small fraction rated it poorly (1-3).

Figure 16. Frequency of use of erasmusintern.org portal by HEIs

As per Figure 17, The most common uses of the erasmusintern.org portal are “**showing students how to use it**” and “**finding traineeship opportunities for students,**” with each cited by over 50% of respondents. This highlights the portal’s dual role as both an informational guide and a practical search tool within HEIs.

A smaller proportion of users (around 14%) access the portal for information about host organisations, which may support quality assurance, partnership development, or informed advising. Additionally, a similar percentage fall into an “other” category, indicating varied or less direct engagement with the platform.

Figure 17. Types of erasmusintern.org information and resources used primarily by HEIs

Suggestions for improvements to the portal

Respondents were offered the opportunity to provide feedback for improvements or changes to the portal that might enhance support to institutions and students. The most frequently mentioned themes included more information about hosts, suggesting that institutions want greater transparency and quality assurance regarding host organisations. Respondents would also like to see improvements in the usability of the interface, specifically a more modern, intuitive and user-friendly design. The simplification of the portal's application process for students also featured strongly. In addition, respondents emphasised the need for multilingual resources and cultural preparation tools. Other ideas raised included better integration with university systems, more curated content, and clearer guidance for both students and institutions.

Respondents were also asked if there were any specific features or functionalities that they would like to see added to the erasmusintern.org portal. Some of the key suggestions included destination guides with safety and accommodation tips, notification system for newly advertised traineeships, simplification and digitisation of the application workflow, expansion of the range of internships, particularly in specialised fields/disciplines.

Figure 18 evidences strong support for the view that increasing awareness of the erasmusintern.org portal would benefit their institutions' international placements. Understanding that this platform is seen as beneficial to IRO's, it is important that the [Erasmusintern.org](https://www.erasmusintern.org) website is sufficiently advertised to IRO's and to students through promotional campaigns.

Figure 18. The extent to which HEIs consider that increasing the awareness of the portal amongst students will benefit the HEIs international traineeship efforts

5. HEI Staff Focus groups findings

5. HEI Staff Focus groups findings:

5.1 Who participated in the focus group?

Putting HEI staff working on sending students on international traineeship at the centre of efforts to improve Erasmus+ traineeships is key to understanding what support is offered to students that go on placements abroad. The DETAS project organised six focus groups in the month of March 2025. These groups address the support provided before, during and after the traineeship period.

The aims of the focus groups were:

- Identify which traineeship support measures work the best for the HEI and for students.
- Understand the issues in the current traineeship procedure from the staff level.
- Identify local and international solutions to these barriers of success that would result in increased student participation in Erasmus+ traineeships.

A total of 49 staff members working on sending but also on receiving students on Erasmus+ traineeships participated in the focus group sessions. The online focus groups were hosted by the University of Limerick (3 sessions), the Erasmus Student Network (1 session) and the European University foundation (2 sessions).

The staff that participated in the focus groups came from a vast range of countries. The figures collected in the registration phase for the focus group show that four out of 10 participants came from HEIs from Central and Eastern European countries (43,3%). A third came from Western European Countries (28,3%) and the remaining third came either from Southern European Countries, the Nordics or the Baltics. The overwhelming number of staff that participated in the focus groups had experience in sending students on international and Erasmus+ traineeships as set out in the aim of the report. Furthermore, some staff, namely those working with University Hospital partnerships also had experience in accommodating international trainee students in their HEI.

5.2 HEI Support before the start of the traineeship

What are the difficulties in getting your students to participate in Erasmus + traineeships?

HEI staff that send students on Erasmus+ traineeships are there to support students during the entirety of the process. They are the people most acutely aware of the problems and barriers that students encounter when faced with the decision to undertake an international traineeship. Identifying these barriers is essential for these staff members so that they can help guide students through them at the beginning stages of the traineeship process.

"The cost associated with international placement for students is astronomical, if they are relocating you can expect about thousands of Euros before you have even landed".

One of the flagged barriers is the cost associated with going on an international traineeship. Just like for Erasmus+ study mobility, support staff mention that the information about the benefits of the Erasmus programme, as well as additional support from the HEI or the company, are important factors in students' decision-making. However, these financial concerns do not only include remunerations or company compensation schemes. They also extend to what students can expect in terms of accommodation in the host country and how a traineeship abroad may impact their housing situation in their home country. HEI staff have noticed that these are predominant aspects that students consider before choosing to participate on an Erasmus+ traineeship.

Other issues that HEI staff members recognise include sector-specific challenges, student motivation, housing scams, and the lack of support of the hosting company in providing sufficient aid when the student arrives for the traineeship. Reflecting on the first barrier, focus group participants suggested that students from certain fields of study have an easier time finding an internship, while in other fields of studies, students need assistance

from staff in finding their traineeship. For the second barrier, HEI staff argued that since the COVID-19 era, there has been an emerging trend of students having lower motivation levels to travel abroad. Moreover, in the case where the traineeship is not a mandatory part of the curriculum, staff witness a clear decrease of urgency to find a traineeship position compared to those where it is part of the curriculum.

"Mandatory and voluntary Erasmus+ traineeships impact staff differently: in mandatory placements, staff prioritise securing a placement for every student, while for voluntary placements the main focus is on ensuring students are genuinely motivated to participate."

Besides tackling the barriers for students, there is also the goal for staff to have students participate in good-quality Erasmus+ traineeships. Many HEI staff agree that developing private-sector partnerships is key in this matter. The reason for this is that it increases trust among students, HEIs and the company, and builds long-lasting relationships between HEIs and the company which is a benefit to all. However, the process of contacting private companies is a time-consuming and resource-intensive one.

Interestingly, companies do not shy away from reporting to HEI staff that there is a lack of official information for them regarding the Erasmus+ programme. Companies share their challenges in understanding the complexities of hosting international students. Some companies are for instance not aware that Erasmus+ funds are typically provided through universities (or other HEIs) and not passed on to employers. The participants also indicated that financial barriers often prevent students from undertaking international traineeships, highlighting the need for careful financial management to ensure students receive the support they need and deserve.

“Some employers use the existence of the Erasmus funding to justify the low or inexistent compensation for their trainees. They may view the Erasmus+ funding as a salary rather than a supplement to their salary.”

Closely related to this information gap is the information on the traineeship itself. Many staff sending students on Erasmus+ traineeships must validate the terms and environment of the traineeship before the student departs, more specifically, whether the announced traineeship is appropriate for the student and complies with internal HEI traineeship policies. This is a time-consuming activity that also relies on the available information online about the proposed traineeship. Accordingly, HEI staff mention that smaller companies have a disadvantage compared to larger companies, as there is generally less information about them on the web, which makes the traineeship approval process more difficult.

What services are currently in place in European HEIs to support Erasmus+ before the traineeships start?

Based on the barriers that staff identify for students and those related to companies, HEI have developed various supporting tools such as using peer-to-peer discussions, hosting information sessions, handing out flyers and email communication to help guide students and increase the offer of quality international traineeships. All these efforts aim to encourage students to undertake an Erasmus+ traineeship or to ensure that their experience before leaving is as good as possible. Some of the guidance is resource-intensive, while others are more of a coordinating nature.

Almost all participants in the focus group mentioned their use of Erasmus Days or international days to communicate the benefits of participating in on Erasmus+ traineeships. This is what they recall as an easy way in which institutions present the programme. Furthermore, some participants also ask professors to take a few minutes during their lectures to present the Erasmus+ traineeship programme and HEI supporting services. These activities are important for staff as they provide an opportunity to promote information about these traineeships to a student audience that may not be

aware of the international opportunities. In addition, other HEIs organise preparatory workshops to help students create their CVs, identify their values, strengths and weaknesses, and assist them in transitioning from academic to professional life.

"The promotion of Erasmus+ traineeship workshops and similar activities that inform students is done through social media and student academic boards such as Canva."

It is important to note that HEIs often translate the Erasmus+ programme into their local languages and try to communicate what the programme does for the local student populations through social media, emails, and academic portals, where students often spend time. These dissemination methods and modes of communication have become increasingly important to reach a broader range of students. Furthermore, several HEIs also offer one-on-one meetings with students to answer the concerns they may have in choosing to go on a traineeship. In these meetings, everything from financial matters to advice is provided and is one of the most resource-intensive ways that HEI supports students. Yet, it helps students understand what is expected of them and how to find the best traineeship for them.

Staff also promote other existing organisations and websites that help students understand what the Erasmus+ traineeship experience entails. Some do this by offering two training sessions per year to explain to students how portals such as the traineeship vacancy board Erasmus Intern or AIESEC work. Furthermore, students are encouraged to look for traineeships on platforms such as LinkedIn, Welcome to the Jungle (a job listing board), [Erasmusintern.org](https://www.erasmusintern.org) or their in-house job vacancy site to apply for traineeship opportunities. This aspect reflects on the guidance role that HEI takes in encouraging students to search independently for the traineeship. Once the student has applied to an opening, the HEI staff suggest students to use tools like Vmock and Careerset to prepare the applicants with preparation interviews. Some HEI staff even do one-on-one interviews with the student before the "real" interview with the company.

On the topic of the help that some HEIs inform companies with guidelines on how to successfully onboard and support international students⁵. Furthermore, other HEIs have an internal ranking system in which private companies are graded by students after the traineeship. When companies do not receive a satisfactory grade, the HEIs staff looks into helping the company improve the Erasmus+ traineeship experience before sending new students to that company. However, this is also a time consuming endeavor and is not done systematically by all HEIs.

What support strategies have worked best?

The participants report that using student ambassadors is the best way to explain to the student population how the Erasmus+ traineeship process takes place. These ambassadors are for the most part former students who have completed their international traineeship. Their main goal is to share their experiences with current students. The information they provide concerns the experiences of living in another country, the financial considerations and practical details. Student ambassadors share their experiences by using social media promotion and explaining in workshops and faculty tours the benefits of the traineeship abroad and the impact theirs had on them. In this, the HEI staff that support sending students on Erasmus+ traineeship act as a guiding role in bringing these former students to the student population.

“For us, the best strategy is peer-to-peer interaction. Former students that have had these Erasmus mobilities talking directly to students that are interested. They provide very personal feedback and practical information.”

Another suggestion from the focus groups is a traineeship career-focused approach. It entails that for both students who have a mandatory Erasmus+ traineeship in their curriculum and those where it is non-compulsory, the entire process is systematically viewed through a student career-focussed lens. In this method, students begin by learning what they can gain from the traineeship and are therefore encouraged to view the experience as a step into their future careers. This approach also has the benefit of

⁵ As an example see DETAS Information toolkit for employerst:
https://detas.erasmusintern.org/publications/toolkit_employers_traineeships.pdf

encouraging students to look for the best possible traineeship that will serve them in the future rather than settling for the first one they find online.

"We spend time encouraging students to think about their wants and needs and what they want to get out of a career, and to apply to their traineeship search. This approach has led to better outcomes and higher quality internships."

In the case that a traineeship is compulsory in the curriculum, HEI staff responsible for sending these students on traineeships agree on the importance of familiarising the students in their first year about the Erasmus+ traineeship opportunities. They engage students' interest through workshops and peer-to-peer learning activities. This is done to counter procrastination in their search for a traineeship. HEI staff note that this approach helps them limit the number of last minute questions posed before the application deadline of students who started searching for their internship too late.

5.3 HEI support for traineeships during the traineeship

What are the most common issues that HEI staff have to deal with during the traineeship?

Participant HEI staff that work on guiding students going abroad agree that the support in the second phase of the traineeship process, when students are abroad, is very different and less easy to provide than in pre-placement stage. The main reason for this is that most HEI have difficulties monitoring the realities of the traineeship, the support and the inclusion initiatives of the company.

"During the traineeship, it is much more difficult to monitor how students are doing abroad."

HEI staff explain that if there are issues with the traineeship they mostly occur in the beginning phase of the placement. One of the most common issues is the trainee housing situation. Participants suggest that students are rarely able to see the accommodation they will be living in for months at a time in-person before they leave for the traineeship. Hence, there are frequent questions for staff to help them access better housing opportunities in case of unsanitary conditions.

Another concern that also coincides in the beginning stage of the traineeship process are questions surrounding cultural adaptation. These do not only include adaptations to the local environment or language. Indeed, switching from the academic sphere into the workplace culture is often a big shock for students participating in Erasmus+ traineeships. This is also one of the major differences with Erasmus+ study exchanges as the work setting is not yet familiar to the students. In the most extreme cases, there are students who as a result of their dislike of the local environment, workload and the reality of the traineeship return home. In these cases the HEI coordinators are then in close contact with the student and the company.

"It is not easy for a university to check the validity of the complaints that students have regarding their traineeship."

"If there is a serious problem, we hope they reach out to us".

Other institutions have developed monitoring mechanisms and send automated feedback forms to their students during their traineeship. Based on the feedback, HEI staff are able to follow-up with the student and then contact the host company if the situation requires

it. Participants noted that automated feedback mechanisms can be sent through email communication or through digital platforms (such as InPlace). These software or apps were initially created during the Covid era to help students in crisis situations or with challenges regarding travelling, lockdowns and other aspects of their placement. However, participants that implemented these mechanisms have continued to use these apps as they see them as being useful even after the Covid era. They argue that through the app they are able to keep track of the student population whilst they are on their traineeship.

"We have an app through which students receive relevant information and can contact us at any point of their traineeship. This is especially helpful during moments of crisis such as the wildfires in Greece a couple of years ago."

In other HEIs where the traineeship is part of the curriculum, the outgoing trainees must report back on their progress and experiences at several stages during the traineeship. In practical terms, students either have to fill in forms or have business-like online meetings with the HEI staff to review exactly what their tasks have been and how they can improve their stay abroad. However, these meetings need to be scheduled beforehand and the focus group participants mentioned that some students go on traineeship abroad during the summer months. Hence, dedicating time and resources for these meetings is key to their success.

What support do you believe is missing for students during traineeship?

During the focus groups, several HEI staff complimented the initiatives that are taken to digitalise through for instance the app and other feedback mechanisms. Considering the advancements of collective messaging, several staff argued that this would revolutionise the way they could offer targeted help to students. On the question of what would prevent them from building these apps, the respondents mentioned a lack of (technical) resources.

"Creating Erasmus traineeships alumni networks would help us."

Besides creating automated messaging tools, the participants also mentioned the importance of community building between students that go on traineeships. One suggestion was to create an alumni network where students could share their experiences and ask for help on the platform to either staff members, former trainees or students that are also pursuing a traineeship but in a different country.

5.4 HEI support for students after the Erasmus+ traineeship has ended

The two remaining focus groups discussed this topic. In terms of the answers to this question the participants expressed that receiving feedback forms is not mandated to obtaining the Erasmus+ grant. Furthermore, virtually all traineeships that are a compulsory part in the curriculum include students having to complete a reflection or post-traineeship report. The report is thereafter assessed by staff and can be a formal part of their degree. This report is then graded with a pass/fail or assigned grade. Once successfully completed, the student receives the corresponding ECTS for completing the traineeship and may sometimes qualify to receive a diploma supplement.

"Formal recognition of the traineeship depends on whether it is mandatory, diploma supplements can also be provided to show specific experiences."

In the case that the student went on a voluntary traineeship, many institutions also ask to fill in a report, however the content of this report is different from the one in the mandatory option. In this one, students “write their story” regarding the traineeship and reflect on their education from the angle of learning in a professional setting. These reports can be used to incite other students to go on traineeships after consent is given by the author. In both curriculum-mandatory traineeships and voluntary ones the HEI usually provides a form to the students that include some of these following aspects:

- Description of the company
- Description of the department
- Overview of responsibilities
- Assessment and reflection on skills development
- Details on visit by tutor/academic (virtual or in-person)
- Competences for formal professional accreditation (sometimes captured in a formal logbook)
- Rating of the placement

Interestingly, one participant suggested that they found an effective model for post-traineeship reflection by asking students to make (ca. 5 mins) formal presentations to outgoing students. This method offers their returning students the opportunity to reflect on what they have learnt from the traineeship and promotes their experience to new students. Another creative initiative from an HEI was to create a photo competition with all the trainee students once they return to the HEI. This activity serves to raise awareness of the placement opportunities, to make international traineeships more attractive, and to encourage students to apply. The participant agreed that students generally view this activity as a fun way to look back on their traineeship and to discuss in informal ways their experiences.

What is the role of institutional HEI Erasmus staff/coordinators after the traineeship?

"We oversee the traineeships but we signpost students to the next relevant support if they come to us afterwards".

HEI staff that help supervise the traineeship process report they have more of a guiding role when students come back from their traineeship. Whilst they cannot help students directly with for instance finding housing, career-guidance or re-integration they can provide returning students with contact numbers of other HEI staff people that can help them with these issues. In other cases, staff responsible for Erasmus+ coordination have discussions with the students when they return home. However, they point out that these are mainly "unstructured" interviews most notably occurring when the student needs to get something signed by the Erasmus coordinator.

"There is no plan to improve our traineeship policy based on the unstructured interviews."

HEI staff are acutely aware of the "post-Erasmus depression" which is a phenomenon whereby students go through a difficult transition as a result of going from a stimulating traineeship environment to a less engaging one in academia. Participants mentioned that the effects can be seamless for some and sometimes quite hard for other students. Yet, the role of Erasmus staff in their view resides outside of the career/traineeship and international education remit. Therefore, this phase of support for the traineeship process is seen by many HEI staff as the one where they have the least impact.

What about career guidance after the traineeship?

Many students undertake a traineeship at the end of their final year and therefore have difficulties in contacting the HEI careers services post-traineeship as the student graduates. Although nearly all participants agreed that career counseling after a traineeship is crucial for employability and can lead to significant success, they emphasized a different focus. Erasmus+ traineeship coordinators see their primary role as motivating students to take up traineeships and ensuring a wide range of opportunities is available.

"We lack specific training to help students reflect on their traineeship."

One innovative idea in light of this discussion was to bring together HEI Erasmus staff and support services to enhance feedback mechanisms. The aim would be to align closer the Erasmus+ traineeship and career services to create synergies. Participants see this as a practical way to address the lack of resources and capacity that currently limits the provision of more comprehensive support.

Reflections on what could help HEI staff evaluate traineeships better in the future?

Focus group participants argue that improving the evaluation of traineeships by HEI staff requires a more holistic and student-centred approach that is possible with the limited resources international offices have. Current practices reveal gaps in key areas of support in student reflection, traineeship (skills) recognition, and emotional support for integrating back into academic life. One of the solutions would be to develop structured mechanisms to support post-mobility reflection. While many institutions acknowledge this importance, relatively few have implemented guiding tools for students to assess their personal and professional development once they return. HEI staff developed several ideas of how these mechanisms can take form:

Making reflection forms/presentations mandatory parts of going on a traineeship will increase

HEI have realised that the number of participants drastically increases when the reflection is an academic obligation. Furthermore, in the cases that it is purely impossible to make it obligatory, there are ways to increase the number of participants such as through formally recognising reflections as a skill for the student to take to his curriculum vitae (CV).

Standardise evaluation templates for companies and students

Frequently HEI report that they do not have a structured way to evaluate the needs of their traineeship process because they lack an overarching narrative of what could change. Creating a standardised evaluation form would help Erasmus HEI staff to act as stakeholders in the university and higher education area to propose improvements in policy.

Increasing synergies with Higher Educational Institutions career offices

Many HEI have inhouse career offices that still do not have much contact with the HEI Erasmus office. By creating synergies between the two, staff from the Erasmus office can more thoroughly bring awareness to the available help career advisors and vice versa. Staff argue that this especially makes sense for the traineeship population as they will have already had work experience through their placement. Moreover, promoting awareness of the role of reflections can help boost employment opportunities of the trainees.

Investing in staff training and broadening awareness of support

The role of Erasmus office staff is to guide students to the relevant people that can help them. However, they are often in the front line when post-traineeship students need assistance to re-enter the home HEI environment. Therefore, it is important that new staff know what support can be given to students who have finished their traineeship and that they can deal with helping guide these students in a suitable manner.

Conclusion

Conclusion

The report reveals that only two-thirds of European higher educational institutions have resources and support mechanisms in place to help students participate in Erasmus+ traineeships. Most of the support is provided at the pre-traineeship stage, when students need help with finding the traineeship, applying for the Erasmus+ grant, and arranging housing and travel. The support that works best to encourage students to participate in non-compulsory Erasmus+ traineeships is utilising traineeship alumni ambassadors, who can explain their experiences to prospective trainee students. A second finding is that while HEIs' staff see it as effective, less than half of European HEIs currently support students in creating a CV, preparing them with mock interviews and workshops or have dedicated sessions on working culture.

The most challenging part for students on a traineeship remains the financial implications. HEIs have been taking two steps in this regard: some only accept students who go on traineeships that include monetary compensation, while others offer additional funds to students beyond the Erasmus+ traineeship grant. Engaging employers is also something that requires more attention, as only a third of European HEIs actively engage with international employers who could host their students. When issues arise during the traineeship, just over half of HEIs have feedback sessions with students. However, while there are best practices, such as emailing, calling, and using phone apps that students can report through in case of emergencies, the majority of HEIs do not have this type of individual support for students when they are abroad in 2025.

Most HEIs send feedback surveys to students after they return from the traineeship. However, the way in which their experience can then be shared for improving the experiences of new students and communication goals varies widely. Some HEIs utilise these experiences to convey the benefits of Erasmus+ traineeships to a new generation of traineeship students, such as by displaying pictures and stories on their websites and other communication channels. Others use them to analyse how they can better support students or contact the employer in case issues are flagged. Notably, fewer than one-third of HEIs solicit feedback from the company. It is during this stage that HEI staff have to recognise the activity.

Overall, this report finds that there are many institutions which do not yet have fledged out Traineeship support mechanisms during the full period of the student cycle. While this report does indicate that there are ongoing developments in HEIs, the advancements remain slow relative to the ambitions being placed on Erasmus+ traineeships. Therefore further research should be conducted on how to close the gap between the HEIs that support students to a great extent and those that do not. Furthermore, other avenues should be explored to determine how national or EU/Erasmus+ programme-level changes can help HEIs in better supporting students for participating in international traineeships.

Digitalising Erasmus Traineeship Application & Support